

Synthesis of 2-phenylimino-3-aryl-4-*S*-benzyl-6-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochloride)

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Abstract : A new series 2-phenylimino-3-aryl-4-*S*-benzyl-6-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochloride) have been synthesized by the interaction of 1-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets with phenyl isocyanodichloride. The newly synthesized compounds have been characterized by analytical and IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral studies.

Keywords : Isodithiobiurets, phenyl isocyanodichloride, 1,3,5-thiadiazines.

Introduction

The heterocyclic systems encompassing thiazole, thiazine, thiadiazine are explored to the maximum extent owing to their pharmacological activities such as development of new fungicides against the causal agent of rice blast disease, *Magnaporthe grisea*¹. Some novel thiazonaphthalimides are used as efficient antitumor and DNA photocleaving agents² and various heterocyclic derivatives arrest the initiation of hepatitis C virus (HCV) RNA synthetase³. Likewise sugar with heterocyclic nucleus are known to have multifaceted biological⁴⁻⁷, pharmacological properties^{8,9} and many of them function as therapeutic agents^{10,11}. Thus the development of new synthetic methods is one of the frontier areas of modern organic synthesis. To expand the above views and application profiles, extensive efforts have been developed for the synthesis of new class of 2-phenylimino-3-aryl-4-*S*-benzyl-

6-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochloride). Here, we now report the method of synthesis of several 2-phenylimino-3-aryl-4-*S*-benzyl-6-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochloride) (**3a-g**). These were synthesized by the reaction of 1-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**1a-g**) with phenyl-isocyanodichloride¹² (**2**). The required 1-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**3a-g**) (Scheme 1) were obtained by the interaction of hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl isothiocyanate¹³⁻¹⁶ with various 1-aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides¹⁷. This maltosyl isothiocyanate remains very important starting material for the construction of heterocycles and also potent irreversible inhibitors of glucose transport in human erythrocytes¹⁸.

R = (a) Phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Certain 2-phenylimino-3-aryl-4-*S*-benzyl-6-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochloride) (**3a-g**) were prepared by the reaction of 1-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**1a-g**) with phenyl isocyanodichloride (**2**) in CHCl_3 . After condensation, the solvent was distilled off to obtain a sticky residue. This residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a pale yellow solid (**3a-g**). The product was found non-desulphurizable when boiled with alkaline lead acetate solution. The specific rotation was measured in chloroform. The results are summarized in Table 1. In spectral analysis^{19–21} IR spectrum of product shows bands due to N–H, Ar–H, ali. C–H, C=O, C=N, C–N, C–O, C–S and C=S stretching and the ¹H NMR spectrum of product distinctly displayed signals due to aromatic protons and maltose ring protons. The Mass spectrum of product was also observed.

formed on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as internal reference. The mass spectra FAB were recorded on a JEOL SX-102 Mass spectrometer. Optical rotation $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ measured on a Equip-Tronics Digital Polarimeter EQ-800 at 31 °C in CHCl_3 . Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on silica gel G for TLC (Merck) and spots were visualized by iodine vapour.

*General procedure for the synthesis of 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-*S*-benzyl-6-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochlorides) (**3a**):*

A mixture of phenyl isocyanodichloride (**2**) (0.173 g, 0.001 mmol in 5 mL CHCl_3) and 1-phenyl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**1a**) in chloroform (1.35 g, 0.001 mmol in 15 mL CHCl_3) was gently refluxed for 4 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was brought to room temperature and

Table 1. Physical data characterization of compounds (**3a-g**)

1-Aryl-5-hepta- <i>O</i> -benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl-2- <i>S</i> -benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1a-g)	g	Product (g)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	R_f value (Petroleum ether : EtOAc, 1 : 1)	$[\alpha]_D^{31}$ CHCl_3	Analysis (%) :	
							Found (Requires)	
							N	S
1-Phenyl-	1.35	3a	80.26	126–128	0.69	+63.89 (c, 0.100)	3.62 (3.65)	4.22 (4.20)
<i>o</i> -Cl-Phenyl-	1.38	3b	92.25	132–134	0.72	+107.3 (c, 1.017)	3.53 (3.58)	4.15 (4.10)
<i>m</i> -Cl-Phenyl-	1.38	3c	93.40	130–133	0.60	+71.40 (c, 0.918)	3.54 (3.58)	4.12 (4.10)
<i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl-	1.38	3d	88.10	125–126	0.54	–39.99 (c, 1.00)	3.56 (3.58)	4.11 (4.10)
<i>o</i> -Tolyl-	1.36	3e	90.02	134–135	0.64	+81.10 (c, 1.00)	3.59 (3.63)	4.19 (4.15)
<i>m</i> -Tolyl-	1.36	3f	86.21	129–130	0.80	+123.1 (c, 0.970)	3.60 (3.63)	4.17 (4.15)
<i>p</i> -Tolyl-	1.36	3g	97.30	120–123	0.60	–58.10 (c, 1.00)	3.61 (3.63)	4.18 (4.15)

Satisfactory C and H analyses found in all cases.

Experimental

General procedure :

All chemicals were research grade. Melting points determined are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in Nujol, KBr on a FT-IR Perkin-Elmer RXI (4000–450 cm^{-1}) spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR measurements were per-

the solvent removed under reduced pressure to obtain sticky residue. This residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a granular pale yellow solid (**3a**). The crude product was purified by chloroform-ether and recrystallized by ethanol-water (1.22 g, 80.26%), m.p.126–128 °C (Scheme 1). The physical

characterization results are summarized in Table 1 (3a-g). Compounds 3b-g were also prepared by similar method.

3a : IR (KBr) : ν 3066.6 (Ar-H), 2960.1 (ali. C-H), 1729.3 (C=O), 1583.1 (C=N), 1377.4 (C-N), 1269.9 (C-O), 1176 (C=S), 1096.6–1026.9 and 936.9 (characteristic of maltose) and 760.5 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : δ 8.25–7.23 (50H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, $3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.09–4.03 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S- CH_2); FABMS (m/z) : 1526 (M^+), 1454 (M-2HCl), 1486 (M- N_2C), 1351 (M-2HCl, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN}$), 1230 (M- N_2C , $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 1053 (HBM $^+$ =M-2HCl, $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$), 976 (HBM- C_6H_5), 948 (HBM- $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 (HBM- $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 918 (HBM- $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 579 (TBG $^+$ =HBM- $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$), 474 (TBG- C_6H_5), 353 (TBG- $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 232 (HBM-TBG, $2\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 135 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2^+$), 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}^+$), 77 (C_6H_5^+) (Found : C, 65.25; H, 4.31; N, 3.65; S, 4.20. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{83}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ requires : C, 65.26; H, 4.32; N, 3.66; S, 4.19%).

3b : IR (KBr) : ν 3066.3 (Ar-H), 2958.9 (ali. C-H), 1728.7 (C=O), 1583.1 (C=N), 1377 (C-N), 1270.4 (C-O), 1176.2 (C=S), 1096.6–1027.5 and 936.9 (characteristic of maltose) and 757.8 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : δ 7.99–7.20 (49H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, $2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_4), 6.10–4.03 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S- CH_2); FABMS (m/z) : 1560 (M^+), 1562 ($\text{M}+2$) $^+$, 1488 (M-2HCl), 1385 (M-2HCl, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN}$), 1264 (M-2HCl, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN}$, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 1053 (HBM $^+$ =M- $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{HCl}$), 976 (HBM- C_6H_5), 948 (HBM- $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 (HBM- $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 918 (HBM- $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 579 (TBG $^+$ =HBM- $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$), 474 (TBG- C_6H_5), 353 (TBG- $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 232 (HBM-TBG, $2\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 135 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2^+$), 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}^+$), 77 (C_6H_5^+) (Found : C, 63.79; H, 4.13; N, 3.53; S, 4.15. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{83}\text{H}_{65}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ requires : C, 63.84; H, 4.16; N, 3.58; S, 4.10%).

3c : $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : δ 8.47–7.20 (49H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, $2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_4), 6.17–3.92 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S- CH_2) (Found : C, 63.80; H, 4.14; N, 3.54; S, 4.12. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{83}\text{H}_{65}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ requires : C, 63.84; H, 4.16; N, 3.58; S, 4.10%).

3d : $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : δ 8.24–7.23 (49H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, $2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_4), 6.09–4.03 (16H, m, mal-

tose ring protons, S- CH_2) (Found : C, 63.79; H, 4.11; N, 3.56; S, 4.11. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{83}\text{H}_{65}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ requires : C, 63.84; H, 4.16; N, 3.58; S, 4.10%).

3e : $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : δ 8.41–7.22 (49H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, $2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_4), 5.81–4.13 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S- CH_2), 2.34 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3) (Found : C, 65.42; H, 4.39; N, 3.59; S, 4.19. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{84}\text{H}_{68}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ requires : C, 65.45; H, 4.41; N, 3.63; S, 4.15%)

3f : $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : δ 8.31–7.20 (49H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, $2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_4), 5.79–3.98 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S- CH_2), 2.34 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3) (Found : C, 65.43; H, 4.40; N, 3.60; S, 4.17. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{84}\text{H}_{68}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ requires : C, 65.45; H, 4.41; N, 3.63; S, 4.15%).

3g : IR (KBr) : ν 3066.3 (Ar-H), 2960.2 (ali. C-H), 1729.3 (C=O), 1509 (C=N), 1377.6 (C-N), 1270 (C-O), 1176 (C=S), 1099.1–1028.7 and 936.9 (characteristic of maltose) and 771.2 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : δ 7.99–7.19 (49H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, $2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_4), 6.10–4.02 (16H, m, maltose ring protons, S- CH_2), 2.40 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3); FABMS (m/z) : 1540 (M^+), 1468 (M-2HCl), 1365 (M-2HCl, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN}$), 1280 (M-2HCl, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN}$, C_6H_5), 1159 (M-2HCl, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN}$, C_6H_5 , $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 1053 (HBM $^+$ =M- $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$), 976 (HBM- C_6H_5), 932 (HBM- $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 918 (HBM- $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$), 579 (TBG $^+$ =HBM- $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$), 474 (TBG- C_6H_5), 353 (HBM-TBG, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 232 (HBM-TBG, $2\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 135 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_2^+$), 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}^+$), 77 (C_6H_5^+) (Found : C, 65.40; H, 4.38; N, 3.61; S, 4.18. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{84}\text{H}_{68}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$ requires : C, 65.45; H, 4.41; N, 3.63; S, 4.15%).

HBM $^+$ = Hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-maltosyl, TBG $^+$ = Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -glucosyl.

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